

Machine Learning for Heart Health Monitoring Website: The Role of Random Forest Algorithms in Disease Prediction

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Abstract

The study's main goal is to use machine learning (ML) techniques to identify chronic heart failure. To replicate the procedure utilized in clinical practice, the study built models based on various combinations of feature categories, including clinical traits, echocardiography, and laboratory results. The phases of the suggested ML technique include feature selection and classification. Early sickness prediction is vital because of the increase in the prevalence of heart disease. The project's major goal is to identify people more likely to develop heart disease based on a range of medical markers. Various methods, including KNN and logistic regression, were used to predict and identify persons with heart disease. This method for predicting cardiac illness improves patient care, simplifies disease diagnosis, and enables the parallel processing of enormous amounts of data. According to the findings, the Random Forest algorithm has the greatest accuracy of 93%.

Keywords: Random Forest; Chronic Heart Failure; heart disease; Logistic Regression; HTML; CSS

1.0 Introduction

Computers can create and use learning methods thanks to a branch of artificial intelligence known as machine learning. We used a variety of supervised and unsupervised learning classifiers to predict and assess the dataset's accuracy. Cardiovascular illnesses are a broad term that refers to a variety of conditions that could damage the heart and circulatory system. Long considered one of the deadliest illnesses to exist, heart disease. “Cardiovascular disease” is the top cause of death worldwide, according to the WHO. (CVD). Four out of every five CVD fatalities are caused by heart attacks or strokes, with one-third of these deaths happening before the age of 70. Heart disease is one of the leading worldwide causes of death. For bettering patient outcomes, early detection and prediction of cardiac illness are

essential. Forecasting the risk of cardiovascular disease has been effectively accomplished using machine learning techniques. These methods use statistical algorithms to analyze huge amounts of patient data to identify the most important risk factors for cardiac disease (Mohan et al., 2019). Blood flow to the heart or brain is blocked, which results in cardiac attacks. Basic medical facilities can monitor blood pressure, glucose, and lipid levels at home in people who are at risk for heart disease. To make accurate choices and offer the public high-quality services, healthcare professionals must possess these skills. The technique that the healthcare organization offers to professionals who lack more knowledge and expertise is crucial because current approaches cannot arrive at reliable conclusions. We predict heart disease based on health parameters using data mining methods and machine learning algorithms like logistic regression, Random Forest, and support vector machines.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

The suggested method's major goal is to forecast the likelihood of developing heart disease to quickly and accurately diagnose the condition. In our strategy, we employ several data mining approaches and machine learning algorithms, including “Naive Bayes”, “k Nearest Neighbor (KNN)”, “Decision tree”, “Artificial Neural Network (ANN)”, and “Random Forest”, to predict the occurrence of heart disease based on a few health-related variables.

2.1 DATA COLLECTION

To develop a heart disease prediction model, a Kaggle dataset containing information on individuals' health, lifestyle, and demographics is necessary. Additionally, the dataset should include the target variable, which represents the presence or absence of heart disease.

Several publicly accessible datasets for heart disease prediction are available, such as the Framingham Heart Study, the Cleveland Heart Disease Dataset, and the Hungarian Institute of Cardiology Heart Disease Dataset. To create a more reliable model, researchers can choose any one of these datasets or combine them for a more comprehensive analysis.

2.2 DATA PRE-PROCESSING

The dataset must first be preprocessed before being used to train our machine-learning model. Data preparation involves several stages, including: dealing with missing values the dataset must be examined for missing values before we can decide how to proceed. One choice is to substitute the missing values with the related feature's mean, median, or mode.

Encoding categorical variables: The gender and smoking status of some aspects in the dataset may be categorical. For usage in our machine learning model, these categorical variables must be transformed into numerical values.

To make sure that all of the features in the dataset have the same range and distribution, we might need to scale the features.

2.3 FEATURES SELECTION

Before training our machine learning model, we must choose the most important features from the dataset. Model performance can be improved by simplifying the model through feature selection. We can use approaches like correlation analysis, principal component analysis, or

recursive feature elimination to discover which features are most important.

2.4 MODEL SELECTION AND TRAINING

The study may begin training the machine learning model once the data has been preprocessed and the features have been chosen (Shah, 2020). The study can forecast cardiac illness using a variety of techniques, including “logistic regression”, “support vector machines”, “decision trees”, and “neural networks”. With the dataset of 304 samples, the study may compare how well different algorithms perform and select the top performer.

Furthermore, the study must separate the dataset into training and testing groups in order to evaluate the performance of the model. By employing an 80:20 ratio for training and testing data, the study can ensure a balance between adequate model training and reliable performance evaluation. Additionally, techniques like k-fold cross-validation may be used to further verify the model and enhance the confidence in its accuracy and generalizability.

2.5 MODEL EVALUATION

We must assess our model's performance on the testing dataset after training. We may assess the effectiveness of our model using several measures, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. For a visual representation of our model's performance, we may also create a confusion matrix.

2.6 DEPLOYMENT

After developing and testing our machine learning model, we can put it into use in a real-world setting. To make our model easily available to healthcare practitioners, we can develop a web-based application or link it with an already-existing electronic health record system.

3.0 DATASET ATTRIBUTES

Table 2:Dataset Attributes

NO.	ATTRIBUTES	DESCRIPTION	VALUES
1	AGE	Age in years	values
2	SEX	Gender of patient	1=male,0=Female
3	CP	Chest pain	Values 0,1,2,3
4	Trestbps	Resting blood pressure	Continuous values/Hg
5	Chol	Cholesterol values in mg/dl	Continuous values in mg/dl
6	Fbs	Fasting blood sugar	1>=120mg/dl 0<120 mg/dl
7	Restecg	Resting Ecg results	Values 0,1,2
8	Thalch	Maximum heart rate achieved	Continuous values
9	Exang	Exercise-induced angina	1=yes,0=no
10	Old peak	ST depression in ECG	Continuous values
11	Slope	In ecg parameter	Values 1,2,3

12	Ca	Number of the major vessel by fluoroscopy	0-3
13	Thal	Defect type	3=normal 6=fixed defect 7=reversible defect
14	num	Diagnosis of heart disease	Yes no

4.0 MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHM

4.1 Logistic regression

The logistic regression machine learning technique is used when the dependent variables can be categorized. The results of logistic regression are generated based on the characteristics that are given.

It is possible to calculate the probability of classification issues with two outcomes using supervised learning methods like logistic regression. It can also be used to forecast many classes. We utilized the sigmoid function, which is:

$\sigma(z) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}}$, in the Logistic Regression model.

We utilized this function to successfully convert any integer into a value between 0 and 1, which we then used to determine the probability of class identification. For instance, there are two categories of heart disease: those who are affected and those who are not.

4.2 Support Vector Machine

Several studies have used the Support Vector Machine (SVM) that Vapnik and Cortes suggested with success for gender categorization issues (Yadav, 2021). The separation hyperplane in an SVM classifier is chosen to reduce the anticipated classification error of the unobserved test patterns. SVM is a potent predictor that can tell one class from another.

SVM places the test image in the class that is farthest from the closest point in the training image. Using the SVM training method, a model that predicts whether the test image corresponds to this class or another was developed. Even if we restrict ourselves to single pose (frontal) detection, SVM still needs a lot of training data to determine the emotional decision boundary, and the computational cost is high.

4.3 Random Forest

Using the SVM training method, a model that predicts whether the test image corresponds to this class or another was developed. Even if we restrict ourselves to single pose (frontal) detection, SVM still needs a lot of training data to determine the emotional decision boundary, and the computational cost is high. High variance is reduced to low variance by the random forest method. One autonomous learning strategy is random forest. Both categorization and regression can be done with it. The formula is also the most adaptable and user-friendly. Trees comprise a woodland. Folklore holds that woodland is stronger the more trees it has. From randomly chosen data samples, random forests create decision trees. They then obtain predictions from each tree and allow users to vote on which is the optimal response.

5.0 WORKING TECHNIQUES OF RANDOM FOREST ALGORITHM

Fig.1 Workflow of The Project

6.0 DATA VISUALIZATION

Fig.2 Frequency Bar Plot

Fig.3 Bar Plot concerning Age, Trestbps, Chol, Thalach, Oldpeak

Fig. 4 Correlation matrix

7.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Our research focused on the use of “data mining” techniques in healthcare for heart disease. We ran several experiments on our heart disease data set using five data mining methods. We are attempting to determine which classification algorithm is better at predicting heart disease by implementing various classification algorithms. And which one is the most accurate? We conducted five tests, all of which were aimed to compare the outcomes of “logistic regression”, “Decision Trees”, “support vector machine”, and “Random Forest”.

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying a form for 'Medic Care Health Specialist'. The form is titled 'Form' and contains the following fields:

- Name: seema ghosh
- phone number: 7003090574
- Age: 23
- Gender: FeMale
- Medical details**
- Chest-pain: 1
- Trest-Bps: 1
- Cholestrol: 1
- DIABETIC: YES
- Rest ECG: 1
- Thalach: 1

The browser's address bar shows the URL: 127.0.0.1:8000/form/. The taskbar at the bottom indicates a temperature of 32°C and a date of 24-03-2023.

Fig. 5 Templates Of The Webpage

8.0 ACCURACY

Accuracy is a term used to describe the percentage of accurate predictions a model produces in classification problems. A measurement statistic used in machine learning, the accuracy score contrasts the ratio of correct predictions made by a model to all predictions made. By dividing the total number of forecasts by the total number of accurate estimates, we can calculate it. Accuracy is one of the most important machine learning success indicators for a classification model.

The method for determining a machine learning model's accuracy is $1 - (\text{Number of misclassified samples} / \text{Total samples})$. Using “logistic regression” following feature selection, the accuracy achieved on training the data was 86%. The highest accuracy achieved using random forest is 93%.

Serial No.	Machine Learning Algorithm	Accuracy
1	Logistic regression	86%
2	Support Vector Machine	88%
3	Random Forest	93%
4	Linear Discriminant	82.8%
5	KNN	82.2%
6	Linear Support Vector Machine	82.8%

9.0 CONCLUSION

It has demonstrated the effectiveness of various machine learning algorithms for predicting heart disease using a web-based application. Based on the results, the Random Forest algorithm outperformed other machine learning techniques, achieving a remarkable accuracy rate of 93%. This finding highlights the potential of Random Forest algorithms as a valuable tool for heart disease prediction in the context of a heart health monitoring website. Other machine learning algorithms examined in this study, including Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine, Linear Discriminant, KNN, and Linear Support Vector Machine, also yielded substantial accuracy rates ranging from 82.2% to 88%. While these algorithms did not reach the same level of accuracy as the Random Forest algorithm, they still demonstrated their potential in predicting heart disease and could provide complementary benefits when used in conjunction with the Random Forest algorithm. The heart health monitoring website harnesses the power of machine learning algorithms to facilitate early detection and diagnosis of heart disease, potentially leading to more effective treatments, better patient outcomes, and lower healthcare costs. By utilizing the Random Forest algorithm in conjunction with other machine learning techniques, the heart health monitoring website can offer healthcare professionals, patients, and researchers a reliable, accurate, and user-friendly tool for monitoring and predicting heart disease. Moreover, the high accuracy of the Random Forest algorithm underscores its potential for broader applications in the field of health monitoring and disease prediction. This study's results may encourage further research and development of web-based applications utilizing the Random Forest algorithm and other machine learning techniques for various health

conditions, contributing to more effective and personalized healthcare solutions. While this study has shown the effectiveness of machine learning algorithms, particularly the Random Forest algorithm, in heart disease prediction, it is essential to acknowledge that there is always room for improvement. Future research could focus on optimizing these algorithms' performance by incorporating additional relevant data, refining feature selection, and improving data preprocessing techniques. Additionally, exploring the potential of deep learning and ensemble methods for heart disease prediction could further enhance the accuracy and reliability of the heart health monitoring website, ultimately benefiting both healthcare providers and patients.

10.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Heart disease is a leading cause of death worldwide, and early prediction of heart disease can significantly improve the prevention and management of this condition. Over the years, numerous studies have employed various machine learning algorithms to predict heart disease with varying degrees of accuracy. This literature review aims to provide an overview of some of these studies and their findings, focusing on the algorithms used and their respective accuracies.

In this study, Rajdhan et al. ((Rajdhan, 2019)) employed a Bayes accuracy algorithm to predict heart disease with an accuracy of 88%. The authors found that the Bayes accuracy algorithm was effective in predicting heart disease, demonstrating a relatively high level of accuracy in comparison to other algorithms used in similar studies. Achieving an accuracy of 75%. Although the decision tree algorithm demonstrated lower accuracy than the Bayes accuracy algorithm used by the study (Pandey ,2013), it still showed promising results for heart disease prediction.

The following research papers are similar in nature, which are given in Table 1 below.

Table 1. The previous studies on heart disease detection using machine learning model.

Paper name	Algorithm used	Accuracy
Heart Disease ml prediction explorer (Rajdhan, 2019)	Bayes accuracy	88%
A Heart disease prediction using decision tree algorithm(Pandey, 2013)	Decision tree	75%
Improving heart disease prediction using feature selection (Mythili T,2013)	Support vector machine	84.85%
Heart disease prediction using data mining techniques(Patel, 2012)	K-nearest neighbor	67%
Heart disease prediction using unsupervised learning (Jagtap, 2011)	Random forest	79%
Heart disease prediction using	logistic regression	85%

logistic regression(Diwakar et al ., 2017)		
Heart Disease ml prediction explorer (Rajdhan et al ., 2019)	Bayes accuracy	89%

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